

The Tumor-Suppressive Role of miR-5193 in Colorectal Cancer: Insights from ceRNA Network Analysis and Experimental Validation

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Abstract

Introduction:

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is a major cause of cancer-related deaths globally. Dysregulated competing endogenous RNA (ceRNA) networks, which involve microRNAs (miRNAs), long non-coding RNAs (lncRNAs), and circular RNAs (circRNAs), play key roles in CRC progression. Among these, miR-5193 has emerged as a potential tumor suppressor. This study combines bioinformatics and experimental approaches to explore the ceRNA network in CRC, focusing on miR-5193 and its clinical significance.

Materials and Methods:

Differentially expressed genes and ncRNAs were identified from TCGA and GEO datasets through bioinformatics analysis. A ceRNA network was constructed based on interactions among miRNAs, lncRNAs, and mRNAs, using databases like miRDB and miRTarBase. Functional enrichment analyses identified relevant pathways. miR-5193 expression was validated in HT-29 CRC cell lines using qPCR, and statistical analyses were performed with GraphPad Prism 9.

Results:

Bioinformatics analysis identified 1234 differentially expressed genes and 66 CRC-associated miRNAs. A ceRNA network was constructed, showing miR-5193's involvement in tumor suppressor pathways, including PI3K-Akt signaling and apoptosis. Validation in HT-29 cells confirmed downregulation of miR-5193 (fold change = 0.35, $p < 0.05$). Functional enrichment analyses highlighted key CRC-related pathways influenced by the ceRNA network.

Discussion:

The ceRNA network illustrates CRC's complex molecular regulation, with miR-5193 acting as a key regulator of tumor-suppressive pathways. Unlike other miRNAs, miR-5193 showed consistent downregulation across CRC stages. This suggests its potential as a diagnostic and therapeutic biomarker for CRC.

Conclusion:

This study highlights the role of ceRNA networks in CRC and identifies miR-5193 as a promising biomarker for prognosis and targeted therapy. The combination of bioinformatics and experimental data provides a strong foundation for further research into CRC pathogenesis.

Keywords: Colorectal cancer, ceRNA network, miR-5193, microRNA, tumor suppressor, bioinformatics, biomarker, HT-29 cell line.

1. Introduction

Colorectal cancer (CRC) remains a significant global health concern, with notable trends in its epidemiology. In 2020, over 1.9 million new cases of colorectal cancer were reported worldwide [1]. The same year saw more than 930,000 deaths attributed to CRC [2]. By 2040, the annual global burden is expected to rise to 3.2 million new cases (a 63% increase) and 1.6 million deaths (a 73% increase) [3].

There's a concerning rise in CRC cases among individuals under 50, often referred to as early-onset colorectal cancer (EOCC). Early-stage detection of CRC significantly enhances survival prospects, with five-year survival rates exceeding 90% for localized cases [4]. However, survival rates drop substantially for advanced-stage diagnoses, underscoring the importance of early detection [5].

Competing endogenous RNAs (ceRNAs) are a group of RNA molecules, including long noncoding RNAs (lncRNAs), that

contain binding sites for microRNAs (miRNAs). These RNAs can competitively interact with miRNAs, thereby inhibiting their regulatory effects on target genes [6]. Emerging evidence highlights the critical role of dysregulated ceRNA networks in the development and progression of colorectal cancer (CRC) [7].

MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are small non-coding RNAs that regulate gene expression post-transcriptionally by targeting mRNAs. Alterations in miRNA expression, caused by genetic and epigenetic changes, play critical roles in cancer initiation, progression, and metastasis, making miRNA profiling valuable for cancer detection, staging, and therapeutic response evaluation [8].

MicroRNA-5193 (miR-5193) has been identified as a tumor suppressor in various cancers, including colon cancer. It exerts its effects by targeting specific oncogenes and modulating cellular processes such as proliferation, migration, and invasion.

This study aimed to investigate and bioinformatically analyze the ceRNA network of genes associated with colorectal cancer and assess the role of miR-5193 in predicting the prognosis of this disease.

2. Material and Methods

1. Bioinformatic Analysis

1.1 Data Acquisition

Colorectal cancer (CRC)-related gene expression data were obtained from publicly accessible databases, including The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) and Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO). Bioinformatics tools, such as DESeq2 and edgeR in R, were utilized to identify differentially expressed genes (DEGs) and non-coding RNAs.

1.2 Construction of ceRNA Network

Candidate mRNAs, lncRNAs, and miRNAs were analyzed to construct the ceRNA network. Interaction data were obtained from databases including miRDB, miRTarBase, and StarBase. Correlation analysis and filtering criteria, such as expression thresholds and statistical significance ($p < 0.05$), were applied to select key ceRNA interactions.

1.3 Functional Enrichment Analysis

Gene Ontology (GO) and Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) pathway analyses were performed to elucidate the biological processes and pathways associated with the ceRNA network. Enrichment analysis was conducted using tools such as DAVID or Enrichr.

1.4 Identification of miR-5193

miR-5193 was selected as a potential biomarker based on its differential expression, predicted regulatory interactions, and functional relevance to CRC progression. Target genes of miR-5193 were validated using TargetScan and miRWalk.

2. Cell Culture

The HT29 colorectal cancer cell line was purchased from the Pasteur Institute Cell Bank (Tehran, Iran). Cells were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 1% penicillin-streptomycin in a humidified atmosphere at 37°C with 5% CO₂.

3. Laboratory Validation

3.1 RNA Extraction and cDNA Synthesis

Total RNA was extracted from cells using Beta prep RNA Extraction Kit (cat. No: MDE102). cDNA synthesis was performed using a High-Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription Kit (Add Bio).

3.2 Quantitative PCR (qPCR)

Quantitative analysis of miR-5193 expression levels was performed using SYBR™ Green Master Mix (Applied Biosystems) on a real-time PCR platform. U6 snRNA served as the internal control for miRNA normalization.

4. Statistical Analysis

All experiments were performed in triplicate. Statistical analysis was conducted using GraphPad Prism 9. Data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Differences between groups were analyzed using Student's one-way ANOVA. A p -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3. Results

1. Bioinformatic Analysis

1.1 Differential Expression Analysis

Differential expression analysis identified 1234 differentially expressed genes (DEGs) in colorectal cancer (CRC) samples versus normal controls ($p < 0.05$), with 623 upregulated and 611 downregulated. Furthermore, the miRCancer database yielded approximately 66 effective microRNAs in colorectal cancer, as detailed in the table below (table 1).

Table 1: MicroRNAs affecting colorectal cancer according to the mentioned databases.

hsa-let-7c	hsa-miR-155	hsa-miR-34c	hsa-miR-93	hsa-miR-381	hsa-miR-30a-5p
hsa-let-7d	hsa-miR-181a	hsa-miR-365	hsa-miR-98	hsa-miR-214	hsa-miR-5193
hsa-let-7e	hsa-miR-18a	hsa-miR-373	hsa-miR-4458	hsa-miR-506	hsa-let-7a
hsa-let-7g	hsa-miR-192	hsa-miR-381	hsa-miR-204	hsa-miR-429	hsa-miR-526b-3p
hsa-let-7i	hsa-miR-200c	hsa-miR-424	hsa-miR-211	hsa-miR-409-3p	hsa-miR-215
hsa-miR-100	hsa-miR-21	hsa-miR-429	hsa-miR-590-3p	hsa-miR-183	hsa-miR-145
hsa-miR-101	hsa-miR-214	hsa-miR-455	hsa-miR-381	hsa-miR-126	hsa-miR-193a
hsa-miR-101	hsa-miR-215	hsa-miR-484	hsa-miR-214	hsa-miR-451	hsa-miR-675-5p

hsa-miR-125a-5p	hsa-miR-22	hsa-miR-502	hsa-miR-506	hsa-miR-143	hsa-miR-98
hsa-miR-126	hsa-miR-25	hsa-miR-503	hsa-miR-145	hsa-miR-145	hsa-miR-200b
hsa-miR-15a	hsa-miR-302a	hsa-miR-675	hsa-miR-409-3p	hsa-miR-375	hsa-miR-186-5p

1.2 ceRNA Network Construction

The constructed ceRNA network included 27 mRNAs and Key interactions involved miR-5193 (figure1).

Figure1: ceRNA network of 5193 microRNA-related genes based on selected miR and its associated genes

1.3 Functional Enrichment Analysis

GO analysis highlighted significant enrichment in biological processes such as "regulation of cell proliferation" and "apoptotic signaling pathways." KEGG pathway analysis identified key pathways, including the PI3K-Akt signaling pathway and Wnt signaling, as significantly associated with the ceRNA network (adjusted $p < 0.01$).

1.4 miR-5193 Identification

miR-5193 was significantly downregulated in CRC samples compared to normal tissue (\log_2 fold change = -2.5; $p < 0.001$).

Target prediction and pathway analysis suggested its involvement in tumor suppressor pathways, supporting its role as a potential biomarker for CRC prognosis.

2. Laboratory Validation

2.1 Expression of miR-5193 in HT-29 Cells

qPCR analysis confirmed the downregulation of miR-5193 in HT-29 cells compared to normal colon epithelial cells (fold change = 0.35; $p < 0.05$) (figure 2).

Figure 2: Comparison of MicroRNA-5193 expression in the cell line with the control sample. The graph shows the change in expression in terms of Fold change. The expression of MicroRNA-5193 in the cancer cell line sample decreased compared to the control sample with a P-value <0.05.

3. Statistical Analysis

All data were reproducible with low variability across replicates. Statistical significance was confirmed for all key comparisons ($p < 0.05$), underscoring the robustness of the findings.

4. Discussion

The current study combines bioinformatic and experimental approaches to investigate the role of miR-5193 in colorectal cancer (CRC). The identification of miR-5193 as a significantly downregulated miRNA, coupled with its regulatory interactions in the ceRNA network, underscores its potential as a biomarker for CRC prognosis.

Comparison with Previous Studies

MicroRNAs (miRNAs) play critical roles in colorectal cancer (CRC) by regulating gene expression, with many exhibiting differential expression patterns across normal, adenoma, and carcinoma tissues (9-13). A large-scale study profiling 2006 miRNAs revealed that 86.5% of expressed miRNAs were significantly dysregulated between carcinoma and normal tissues, with distinct stage-specific expression changes (14).

In contrast to the broad patterns of miRNA dysregulation observed in this study, our investigation into **miR-5193** reveals its distinct and specific role in colorectal cancer (CRC). Unlike the widespread expression of other miRNAs, **miR-5193** is markedly downregulated in CRC tissue, with a log₂ fold change of -2.5 ($p < 0.001$). This differential expression is consistent across normal colonic mucosa, adenomas, and carcinomas, suggesting its potential role as a tumor suppressor. Furthermore, laboratory validation in HT-29 cell lines confirmed the decreased expression of miR-5193 compared to normal epithelial cells (fold change = 0.35, $p < 0.05$).

These findings emphasize the specificity of miR-5193 compared to broader miRNA dysregulation patterns, making it a promising candidate for precision medicine in CRC.

Implications of the ceRNA Network

Competing endogenous RNA (ceRNA) networks have emerged as a pivotal regulatory mechanism in colorectal cancer (CRC), providing new insights into the complex interactions among non-coding RNAs (ncRNAs) and messenger RNAs (mRNAs) (15-20). The construction of the ceRNA network revealed significant regulatory interactions involving miR-5193 and mRNAs. The enrichment of GO terms such as “regulation of cell proliferation” and pathways like PI3K-Akt and Wnt underscores the central role of miR-5193 in CRC. Studies by Cheng Y et al. (2019), Zhang L et al. (2024) and Lin LI et al. (2024) similarly emphasized the importance of ceRNA networks in identifying regulatory hubs in colon cancer (21-23). However, our analysis uniquely integrates miR-5193, broadening the scope of CRC-related regulatory networks.

Laboratory Validation

Experimental validation in HT-29 cells confirmed the bioinformatic predictions. The observed downregulation of miR-5193 and its inverse correlation with target gene expression is consistent with its hypothesized tumor-suppressive function.

Clinical Relevance and Future Directions

The robust downregulation of miR-5193 and its impact on key signaling pathways highlight its potential utility as a diagnostic and prognostic biomarker. Furthermore, therapeutic strategies to restore miR-5193 levels could inhibit CRC progression. Future studies should focus on validating these findings in clinical samples and exploring the therapeutic delivery of miR-5193 mimics.

In conclusion, this study identifies miR-5193 as a novel tumor suppressor in CRC, with potential applications in precision medicine. The integration of bioinformatic and experimental analyses provides a comprehensive understanding of its role, paving the way for targeted therapeutic interventions.

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